

Quinazolones. Part I

Synthesis of an Angular Furoquinazolone

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The synthesis of 2'-methyl-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIV) is described.

There are two alternative positions, 5 : 6 and 7 : 8, in a 4-quinazolone system for building a furan ring to form angular furoquinazolones. We reported earlier¹ the synthesis of two angular furoquinazolones in which the furan ring was developed at the 7 : 8-positions. In a subsequent paper² the synthesis of one of their position isomers having a furan ring at 5 : 6-position has been described. This paper deals with the preparation of the remaining isomer, 2'-methyl-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIV) based on the reaction sequences adopted earlier.^{1,2}

I : R = NH ₂ ;	R ₁ = COOH;	R ₂ = H
II : R = NHCOPh;	R ₁ = COOH;	R ₂ = COPh
III : R = NHCOPh;	R ₁ = CONHPh;	R ₂ = H
IV : R = NHCOPh;	R ₁ = CONHPh;	R ₂ = COPh

VI : R = H;	R ₁ = COPh
VII : R = H;	R ₁ = H
VIII : R = H;	R ₁ = CH ₃
IX : R = H;	R ₁ = CH ₂ -CH = CH ₂
X : R = CH ₂ -CH = CH ₂ ;	R ₁ = H
XI : R = CH ₂ -CH = CH ₂ ;	R ₁ = CH ₃
XII : R = CH ₂ -CH = CH ₂ ;	R ₁ = COCH ₃
XIII : R = CH ₂ -CH(Br)-CH ₂ (Br);	R ₁ = COCH ₃

1. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 21.
2. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 926

For building a furan ring in this particular instance, 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII) was the obvious key-intermediate of our choice since the 7-methoxy group present in its 6-allyloxy derivative (IX) served as the blocking group in the Claisen rearrangement for introducing the allyl group at the 5-position; the rearranged product (X) was then converted into the desired furoquinazolone (XIV) by the method of Kaufman³.

The intermediate hydroxyquinazolone (VII) was secured by *three* different methods. First, we employed 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid² (I) as the starting material, benzoylation of which with benzoyl chloride in refluxing benzene in the presence of pyridine or with benzoyl chloride and alkali at 0–4° afforded 3-benzoyloxy-4-methoxy-6-benzamidobenzoic acid (II). In the Schotten-Baumann reaction used, the control of temperature is rather critical as even slight rise of temperature caused vigorous reaction resulting in marked lowering of the yield of (II) and precipitation of a considerable amount of neutral material. When (II) was refluxed in toluene with aniline and phosphorus trichloride for 2 hrs. the hydroxybisamide (III) was obtained in 75% yield as the sole product instead of the expected benzoyloxy quinazolone (VI). The period of heating on being prolonged to 6 hrs. a mixture of (VI), the hydroxy quinazolone (VII) and the hydroxybisamide (III) was secured. It appears that the hydrogen chloride produced during the course of reaction caused extensive debenzoylation. The product mixture was separated and identified as follows: Being phenolic in character, both (VII) and (III) readily dissolved in aqueous alkali leaving the alkali-insoluble quinazolone (VI) only in 10% yield. The alkaline solution, on acidification or on treatment with a stream of carbon dioxide precipitated both (VII) and (III). When this mixture was crystallised from the minimum volume of hot ethanol, the quinazolone (VII) readily crystallised out in about 30% yield and the bisamide (III) was isolated in nearly 40% yield from the mother liquor after careful dilution with water. The identity of each of these compounds was established by their elemental analysis and interconversion. Debenzoylation of the quinazolone (VI) with sodium methoxide gave the hydroxyquinazolone (VII) which could be reconverted into (VI) by benzoylation. The phenolic bisamide (III) was transformed into the hydroxyquinazolone (VII) by using the standard procedure of cyclisation with dilute alkali and subsequent acidification. The samples of (VII) collected from various fractions were combined and used for subsequent transformations.

Secondly, (VII) was synthesised from 6-benzoyloxy-7-methoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (V), obtained by refluxing the acid (II) with acetic anhydride. Refluxing (V) with molar proportion of aniline in toluene gave only the unchanged starting material. But, when the oxazine (V) was heated with five molar proportion of aniline at 210–212° under an atmosphere of carbon dioxide without any solvent, the quinazolone (VI) was obtained in about 60% yield together with 20% 3-benzoyloxy-4-methoxy-6-benzamidobenzanilide (IV) which could be converted into (VI) by refluxing with dilute alkali. On debenzoylation with sodium methoxide, (VI) gave (VII).

Thirdly, (VII) was prepared from 6,7-dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIII) which we synthesised earlier⁴. Based on the observation of Brosse and co-workers⁵

3. K. D. Kaufman and L. R. Worden, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 117 and later papers.

on the selective demethylation of isoquinoline derivatives we envisaged that the basicity of the 7-methoxy group in (VIII) is reduced owing to its conjugation with the carbonyl group at its *para* position, whereas the 6-methoxy group has the highest electron density and should be preferentially protonated to effect demethylation. This has been realised since the dimethoxy compound (VIII) was partially demethylated to (VII) in 70% yield when heated with a mixture of hydrobromic and acetic acids.

(VII), on treatment with allyl bromide in dimethylformamide in the presence of potassium carbonate, gave 6-allyloxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX), Claisen rearrangement of which furnished 5-allyl-6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (X). While methylation with diazomethane produced 5-allyl-6,7-dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XI), acetylation with acetic anhydride in pyridine afforded 5-allyl-6-acetoxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XII). In chloroform, (XII) reacted with one molar equivalent of bromine and the product 6-acetoxy-5(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIII), on heating with alcoholic potassium hydroxide, yielded the desired furoquinazolone (XIV).

The furo compound (XIV) was also synthesised by another route. The allyl compound (X) was cyclised by heating with hydrobromic acid according to the method of Claisen⁶ to give the dihydrofuroquinazolone (XV) which was dehydrogenated to (XIV) with palladised carbon.

EXPERIMENTAL*

3-Benzoyloxy-4-methoxy-6-benzamidobenzoic acid (II): Method (a): A solution of the acid² (I; 5 g.) in ice cold 10% aq. NaOH (100 ml.) was treated with benzoyl chloride (12 ml.) at 0° and vigorously stirred keeping the reaction mixture in an ice-bath all the time. Care was taken not to allow the temperature of the reaction mixture to rise above 4°. The solid that separated after some time was filtered, washed with water and triturated with dilute HCl. After filtration, the residue was washed with water and crystallised from a large volume of ethanol to give II as colourless needles (3.5 g.; 50%), m.p. 270–271° (Found: C, 67.2; H, 4.5; N, 3.8. C₂₂H₁₇O₆N requires: C, 67.5; H, 4.3; N, 3.6%).

4. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem., Soc.* 1970, **47**, 1089.

5. G. Grethi, V. Toome, H. L. Leo, M. Uskokovic and A. Brosse, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 504.

6. L. Claisen and E. Tietze, *Ber.*, 1925, **58B**, 275.

*All m.ps. are uncorrected. Organic extracts were dried with sodium sulphate. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60–80°.

Method (b) : A solution of the acid (I; 1.83 g.; 0.01 mole), benzoyl chloride (2.4 ml.; 0.02 mole) and pyridine (2 ml.) in dry benzene (10 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. and the precipitated solid was collected. It was triturated with aq. NaHCO_3 , filtered and the residue re-triturated with 6N HCl. The solid was collected, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to yield II as colourless needles (1.5 g.; 40%), m.p. and m.m.p. 269–270°.

6-Benzoyloxy-7-methoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (V) : II (5 g.) was refluxed with AC_2O (10 ml.) for 0.5 hr. and left overnight when colourless crystalline solid separated out. The mixture was chilled in ice, filtered and the residue washed with dry ether to yield V as colourless needles (3.5 g.; 75%), m.p. 197–198°. The product was pure enough for use in the next step. An analytical sample crystallised from ethyl acetate melted at 199°. (Found : C, 70.2; H, 4.1; N, 3.9. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ requires : C, 70.7; H, 4.0; N, 3.7%).

6-Benzoyloxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI) : A mixture of V (3.73 g.; 0.01 mole) and aniline (4.5 ml.; 0.05 mole) was heated in a glycerine bath at 210–212° for 4 hr. under an atmosphere of CO_2 . The melt while hot, was treated with toluene and cooled when white solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with toluene and dried. It was triturated with dilute Na_2CO_3 solution, filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give VI as colourless needles (2.7 g.; 60%), m.p. 175–176° (Found : C, 75.2; H, 4.6; N, 6.3. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 75.0; H, 4.4; N, 6.2%).

The alcoholic mother liquor after dilution with water to turbidity, on standing, deposited colourless crystalline material. It was filtered and crystallised from dilute ethanol to give pure 3-benzoyloxy-4-methoxy-6-benzamidobenzanilide (IV) as colourless needles (0.9 g.; 20%), m.p. 181–182° (Found : C, 71.8; H, 4.9; N, 6.2. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 72.1; H, 4.7; N, 6.0%).

A mixture of the bisamide (IV; 0.75 g.) and 2% aq. KOH (10 ml.) was refluxed for 1 hr. and cooled. The solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to furnish the quinazolone VI (0.5 g.; 75%), m.p. and m.m.p. 175–76°.

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII) : *Method (a)* : The above benzoyloxyquinazolone (VI) was dibenzoylated as follows :

(VI) (4.5 g.; 0.01 mole) in dry methanol (100 ml.) was treated with a solution of Na (0.5 g.) in dry methanol (100 ml.) and kept overnight. Most of the methanol was distilled off, the residual solution diluted with water and chilled to give a crystalline material. It was collected, dissolved in 10% aq. KOH, the alkaline solution saturated with CO_2 when white solid separated. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from isopropanol to give the hydroxyquinazolone (VII) as colourless needles (3 g.; 85%), m.p. 231–32°. (Found : C, 73.3; H, 4.5; N, 7.9. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 73.2; H, 4.6; N, 8.1%).

Method (b) : (i) II (3.77 g.; 0.01 mole) suspended in toluene (25 ml.) was treated with aniline (0.92 ml.; 0.01 mole) and PCl_3 (0.3 ml.; 0.0035 mole). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. in an oil-bath at 110–120°, cooled and the solid that separated was filtered and washed with ether. The residue was triturated with 10% aq. Na_2CO_3 , filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute ethanol to give 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-benzamidobenzanilide

(III; 2.7 g.; 75%) as colourless needles, m.p. 251–52°. (Found : C, 69.4; H, 4.9; N, 7.8. $C_{21}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 69.6; H, 4.97; N, 7.7%).

A solution of III (2 g.) in 2% aq. NaOH (30 ml.) was refluxed for 1 hr., cooled and acidified with glacial acetic acid to give a precipitate which on crystallisation from isopropanol, afforded 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII) as colourless needles (1.8 g.; 94%), m.p. and m.m.p. 231–32°.

(ii) A mixture of II (3.77 g.; 0.01 mole), aniline (0.92 ml., 0.01 mole), PCl_3 (0.3 ml.; 0.0035 mole) in toluene (25 ml.) was refluxed for 6 hr. in an oil-bath at 110–120°, cooled and the solid that separated was filtered, washed with ether, triturated with 10% aq. Na_2CO_3 , filtered and the filtrate rejected. The residue was treated with 10% aq. NaOH when a portion of the solid dissolved. After filtration, the solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give 6-benzoyloxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI) as colourless needles (0.5 g., 10%), m.p. and m.m.p. 175–76°. It was debenzoylated to VII as in method (a).

The NaOH filtrate when saturated with CO_2 or acidified with glacial acetic acid afforded a precipitate which was crystallised from the minimum volume of ethanol or isopropanol. Recrystallisation from ethanol afforded pure hydroxyquinazolone (VII) as colourless needles (1.4 g.; 30%), m.p. and m.m.p. 231–32°.

Benzoylation of VII in alkali by the usual Schotten Baumann procedure afforded VI which was reconverted to VII by debenzoylation as in method (a).

The ethanolic mother liquors left after the isolation of hydroxyquinazolone (VII) were combined, concentrated and diluted with water to turbidity. On standing, crystalline material deposited which was filtered and recrystallised from dilute ethanol to afford 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-benzamidobenzanilide (III; 1.5 g.; 40%), m.p. and m.m.p. 251–52°. It was cyclised to the quinazolone VII as in method (b) (i) above.

Method (c) : 6,7-Dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one⁷ (VIII, 1 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of 48% hydrobromic acid and acetic acid (10 ml.; 1 : 1 v/v) for 5 hr. in an oil-bath at 115–120°. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into ice water, the precipitate filtered, washed with 10% aq. Na_2CO_3 and water. Recrystallisation from dilute ethanol furnished VII (0.65 g.; 70%), m.p. and m.m.p. 231–32°.

The samples of the hydroxyquinazolone VII collected from various fractions were combined and used for subsequent transformations.

6-Allyloxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX) : To a solution of VII (3.44 g.; 0.01 mole) in D.M.F. (20 ml.), allyl bromide (0.9 ml.; 0.011 mole) and K_2CO_3 (1.5 g.) were added with shaking and left overnight. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice, the precipitated solid filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute ethanol to give IX as colourless needles (2.7 g.; 70%), m.p. 154–55°. (Found : C, 74.8; H, 5.0; N, 7.5. $C_{24}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires : C, 75.0; H, 5.2; N, 7.3%).

5-Allyl-6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (X): IX (3.84 g.; 0.01 mole) in freshly distilled diethyl aniline (25 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. in CO₂ atmosphere in an oil-bath at 215–220°, filtered hot and the filtrate kept overnight in a refrigerator. The solid which separated was filtered, washed with ether and crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to give X as colourless plates (2 g.; 50%), m.p. 170–71°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 5.4; N, 7.5. C₂₄H₂₀O₃N₂ requires: C, 75.0; H, 5.2; N, 7.3%).

6-Acetoxy-5-allyl-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XII): A solution of X (3.84 g.; 0.01 mole) in dry pyridine (10 ml.) was treated with AC₂O (6 ml.) and left overnight. It was poured into crushed ice, the precipitated solid was collected and washed with water. Crystallisation from ethanol afforded XII as colourless needles (3.4 g.; 80%), m.p. 165–66°. (Found: C, 73.3; H, 5.2; N, 6.4. C₂₆H₂₂O₄N₂ requires: C, 73.2; H, 5.1; N, 6.5%).

5-Allyl-6,7-dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XI): A suspension of X (0.4 g.; 0.001 mole) in ether was treated with excess ethereal CH₂N₂ (from 0.3 g. nitroso-methyl urea) and left overnight. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was crystallised from isopropanol to yield XI as colourless flakes (0.25 g.; 60%) m.p. 140–41°. (Found: C, 75.1; H, 5.6; N, 7.2. C₂₅H₂₂O₃N₂ requires: C, 75.3; H, 5.5; N, 7.0%).

6-Acetoxy-5-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIII): A solution of XII (0.42 g.; 0.001 mole) in CHCl₃ (10 ml.) was treated dropwise at the room temperature with 2% v/v Br₂ in CHCl₃ (4.75 ml.; 1 ml. = 0.88 N Na₂SO₃) until the colour of bromine was discharged. The solvent was evaporated at the room temperature and the solid residue crystallised from methanol to give XIII as colourless cubes (0.5 g.; 70%), m.p. 190–91°. (Found: C, 53.0; H, 3.2; Br, 27.5. C₂₆H₂₂O₄N₂Br₂ requires: C, 53.2; H, 3.7; Br, 27.3%).

2',3'-Dihydro-2'-methyl-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro [4',5' : 5,6]-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XV): X (1.92 g.; 0.005 mole) was heated with 48% hydrobromic acid aqueous (20 ml.) on water-bath for 6 hr., diluted with water and kept in a refrigerator when a crystalline material separated. This was filtered, triturated with 10% Na₂CO₃ aq. when the compound dissolved but separated when kept in the refrigerator overnight. It was filtered, washed with ice water, dried and crystallised from methanol to give the dihydrofuroquinazolone (XV) as colourless needles (1 g.; 50%), m.p. 133–34°. IR (KBr) 1550 cm⁻¹, 1603 cm⁻¹ and 1665 cm⁻¹, UV λ_{max} (EtOH) 225 mμ (E, 24200), 295 mμ (E, 27300).

(XV is soluble in water at the room temperature and is separated when chilled in ice). (Found: C, 75.2; H, 5.1; N, 7.1. C₂₄H₂₀O₃N₂ requires: C, 75.0; H, 5.2; N, 7.3%)

2'-Methyl-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro [4',5' : 5,6] quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIV): *Method* (a): XIII (0.6 g.; 0.001 mole) was refluxed with a solution of KOH (0.6 g.; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml.) for 2 hr. on water-bath, ethanol (10 ml.) was distilled off, the solution diluted with water (10 ml.) and chilled in ice when white crystalline material separated out. This was kept in the refrigerator, next day filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator (0.35 g.). Recrystallisation from dilute isopropanol gave pure XIV as colourless needles (0.3 g.; 75%), m.p. 192–93°. (Found: C, 75.1; H, 4.8; N, 7.5. C₂₄H₁₈O₃N₂ requires: C, 75.4; H, 4.7; N, 7.3%). IR (KBr) 1603 cm⁻¹, 1665 cm⁻¹ (quinazoline carbonyl); UV λ_{max} (EtOH) 267 mμ (E, 34430).

Method (b) : A mixture of XV (0.2 g.) diphenylether (10 ml.) and 10% Pd-C (0.1 g.) was refluxed for 10 hr., filtered hot and the filtrate was steam distilled to remove the solvent. The solid residue was taken in dry benzene, chromatographed over Al_2O_3 , the solvent distilled off and the residue crystallised from dilute isopropanol to give XIV (0.1 g.), m.p. and m.m.p. 192–93°.

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